

ASSESSING LIFE SKILLS OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHER

Dr. Harneet Billing

Assistant Professor, Department of Education

Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University, Fatehgarh Sahib

ABSTRACT

In the growing complexities of life, an individual needs to be equipped with life skill so that they are able to face the stress of the life and adjust to the ever-changing world around. The responsibility of preparing the students to face the outside world lies with the teachers. However for that they need to be the possessors of these skills themselves. The objective of this study was to assess the levels of life skills of prospective teachers enrolled as trainees in an integrated teacher education programme. A descriptive survey was done with the help of self-administered questionnaires prepared in English. The present study was conducted on 101 teacher trainees. The results revealed that gender and father literacy status did not cause any significant difference in the life skills of teacher trainees. However mother's literacy level and family type caused significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers.

Keywords: Life skill, teacher trainees, gender, parental qualification, family type

INTRODUCTION

WHO defines life skills as “the abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with demands and challenges of everyday life.” The person needs to be flexible in approach so that he/she may adjust in ever-changing circumstances of life. In the present times of stress and anxiety one needs to be positive and forward looking, even in difficult and hard times.¹ We are witnessing a sharp shifts in our lives with the advent on technology which has marked deeper influences on our education, work place and our home life. These demands for development of new life skills and a new set of ways and systems to

deal with the demands of life. Life skills “can help people to make informed decisions, communicate effectively and develop coping and self-management skills that may help an individual to lead a healthy and productive life.” The responsibility of teaching and inculcating life skills in youth lies with each member of the society, teachers being the actual torch bearers. It is thus essential that they themselves possess life skills and a favorable attitude to work for their inculcation.

The Ten core life skills as laid down by WHO are:

1. Critical Thinking
2. Creative Thinking
3. Decision Making
4. Problem Solving
5. Self Awareness
6. Effective Communication
7. Interpersonal Relationship
8. Empathy
9. Coping with Stress
10. Coping with Emotions

NCFTE, 2009 clearly put in words that A teacher needs to be prepared in relation to the needs and demands arising in the school context, to engage with questions of school knowledge, the learner and the learning process. Every person has ability of thinking and making ethical decisions independently or in a group. It is essential to sensitize students regarding emotions then only they can survive in the world of satisfaction. To understand others, cooperation, social responsibility and good interpersonal relations are essential for prospective teachers.² NCF, 2005 acknowledged Adolescent Education and Life Skills linked to health, consumer rights and legal literacy as important areas in school education and included accordingly in secondary school curriculum. After 2005, over countrywide debate, sex education was restructured as the Adolescence Education Program (AEP) which focused on enhancing life skills among the adolescents, so that they can be

responsible to deal the real life situations.³ it may be inferred that all policy documents on educational reform have suggested and realized the need to include life skill education for the young generation of the country. Education system need to drift from the traditional practices imparting knowledge to the students rather it needs to train them to apply this knowledge to their real life situations, think out of the box, develop new ideas and develop competence to solve problem and take decisions. Teachers role thus become very vital and important. the teachers themselves need to be trained first with life skill elements so that in future they would be able to cope with adolescents'' and youth's related issue and events.³

REVIEW OF RESEARCH LITERATURE

Life skill educator-teachers also perceived positive changes in the students in the program in class room behavior and interaction. LSE integrated into the school mental health program using available resources of schools and teachers is seen as an effective way of empowering adolescents (Kishore and Srikala,2010)⁴. Life skills empower young people to take positive action to protect them and promote health and positive social relationships. It also entails being able to establish productive interpersonal relationships with others. In the present paper the investigator goes through the importance of life skills, various life skills, life skill education and the benefits imparting life skill education in our curriculum(Aparna and Rakhee,2011)⁵ Young et al., (2003) revealed that life skills oriented physical education curriculum increased the magnitude of effects on physical activity behaviour in high school girls⁶. Tarmyan (2003) found that life skills training program plays major role in providing of psycho-social specificity of children and adolescents⁷. Zahra et al., 2013, indicated that life skill training have a significant positive effect on social development and emotional adjustment.⁸

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The result of the study will be helpful to the educators, teachers and teacher educator to develop an insight into the status of life skill of the future teachers. It

will also help the curriculum planners and designers of teacher education programmes.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. to assess the level of life skills in prospective teachers.
2. to compare the life skills in prospective teachers in relation to gender, parental literacy level and family type.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. Prospective teachers possess high level of life skills
2. Male and female teacher trainees do not differ significantly in their life skills.
3. Father literacy level doesnot cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers
4. Mother literacy level doesnot cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers
5. Family type doesnot cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers

SAMPLE

The present study used descriptive survey method to assess the life skills of teacher trainees enrolled in integrated teacher training programme. 101 teacher trainees were included in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GENDER AND LIFE SKILL OF TEACHER TRAINEES

Mean value for life skills in male teacher trainees was found to be 48.86 while for female trainees, it was found to be 49.03. t- value obtained to test the significance of the mean difference was calculated to be 0.904 which is found to be not significant at 0.05 level. Hence ,the null hypothesis that the Male and female teacher trainees do not differ significantly in their life skills is accepted .

PARENTAL QUALIFICATION:

The influence of parental qualifications on the life skills was assessed with respect to literacy status of father and mother separately.

The influence of father literacy level on the life skills of the teacher trainees was tested by the 't' test. Analysis of the data revealed that the life skill scores of teacher trainees whose father was literate (M=48.36) were higher than those whose father was not literate (M= 37.23).

The 't' value ($t= 4.73$) obtained to the test the significance of difference is found to be significant at 0.01 level .Hence ,the null hypothesis that Father literacy level doesnot cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers is rejected

Similarly the influence of mothers literacy level on the life skills of the teacher trainees was tested by the 't' test. It was found that the teacher trainees whose mother was literate (M=46.88) were higher than those whose mother was illiterate (M=41.88)

the 't' value obtained to the test the significance of difference is found to be significant at 0.05 level .Hence ,the null hypothesis that mother literacy level doesnot cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers is rejected .

FAMILY TYPE

The variable was studies with respect to the fact whether the trainees lived in a joint family set up or a nuclear family set up.The influence of family type (nuclear or joint) on the life skills of the teacher trainees was tested by the't' test . The mean value on life skills for trainees living in nuclear family (M=33.78) was found to be less than for those living in joint family (M=43.18).

the 't' value obtained to the test the significance of difference is 2.99 which is found to be significant at 0.01 level .Hence, the null hypothesis Family type does not cause any significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers is rejected.

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals that the

1. Male and female teacher trainees do not differ significantly in their life skills.
2. Father's literacy level causes significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers
3. Mother's literacy level causes significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers
4. Family type causes significant difference in the life skills of prospective teachers

It may thus be inferred that as parental education was seen to be significantly associated with difference in life skill levels of trainees, the policy of compulsory primary education to all should be strengthened. Family values need to be strengthened so as to develop life skills in an individual.

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